

Design and analysis of 2×1 photonic multiplexer operating at CMOS compatible voltages for photonic integrated circuits

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Abstract—In this work, we design and study a photonic multiplexer (PM) based on electro-optic effect and mode-coupling mechanism using lithium niobate on insulator (LNOI). The constructed PM works with CMOS compatible driving voltages, offers low losses and low cross-talks. The finite-difference beam propagation method (FD-BPM) is used for numerical simulation to evaluate the performance of the photonic multiplexer. The various design parameters have been tuned to obtain the optimized performance of the photonic multiplexer. The presented PM exhibits an insertion loss of 1.9206 dB with a single driving voltage of 3.3 V.

Index Terms—Lithium niobate on insulator (LNOI), directional coupler, photonic multiplexer, photonic ICs, photonic logic gates

I. Introduction

The research on photonic integrated circuits has emerged from the last decades, which integrates active and passive photonic components in a monolithic or heterogeneous way on a single chip. The photonic IC platforms such as SoI [1], SiN [2] and InP [3] are being developed to industrial scale. Further, the heterogeneous integration of lithium niobate (LN) with SoI waveguides has attracted significant interest, which enabled electro-optical tunable resonators, Mach-Zehnder modulators and Mid-IR modulators. Hence, a comprehensive review of LNOI is discussed in [4]. Recently, thin-film LNOI has become commercially available and a detailed fabrication process of LNOI wafers is discussed by Gorazd Poberaj et al [5].

II. Design of Photonic Multiplexer

The proposed photonic multiplexer works based on the on-off switching mechanism of the 2×2 directional coupler.

A. Design of 1×1 photonic switch

The architecture and cross-sectional view of the 1×1 on-off photonic switch are shown in Fig.1. The straight waveguide is used for light transmission from the input port to the output port when an external electric field is applied to the electrode configuration. The parallel waveguide inside the switch is used for coupling the input light in the absence of the external electric field using

s-bent waveguide and tapered waveguide. The tapered waveguide is used to reduce the light intensity as it travels in the tapered section and serves as the terminated port. By removing one of the input port of traditional 2×2 directional coupler and considering one output port, the input-output electric field relations in terms of power-coupling coefficient κ is derived as follows. The electric field available at the terminated port (E_{term}) and in the output port (E_{out}) is expressed using equations (1) and (2) and these equations act as the characteristic equations for the 1×1 on-off photonic switch.

$$E_{term} = -jE_{in}\sin(\kappa z) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{out} = \cos(\kappa z) \quad (2)$$

where E_{in} is the electric field of the input light, κ is the cross power coupling coefficient and z is the propagation direction. The BPM result of the designed 1×1 photonic switch is shown in Fig.2 for the ON-state and OFF-state. Based on the designed 1×1 photonic switch, the proposed photonic multiplexer is constructed using two 1×1 photonic switches as follows.

B. Design of 2×1 photonic multiplexer

The 1×1 photonic switch is configured to form a photonic multiplexer as shown in Fig.3. The proposed photonic multiplexer is differing from the existing digital multiplexer principle, where, for one select/control value one input is allowed to propagate and for the complement value, the second input is allowed to propagate. The inherent drawback of this mechanism is by default any one of the input is allowed to propagate. In the case of a photonic multiplexer, if one of the inputs is always allowed to pass then there will not be control over that, it is expected to have control over both the inputs separately. Hence we need two dedicated control signals for each input, which are $Vc1(t)$ for first input $E1(z)$ and $Vc2(t)$ for second input $E2(z)$. By controlling the value of $Vc1(t)$ and $Vc2(t)$ first input or second input will be allowed to pass. For the photonic multiplexer. the relation between the input-output electric fields with respect to the external control/driving voltage is expressed as follows using equations (3)-(5).

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$$Y_1(z) = V_{c1}(t)E_1(z) \quad (3)$$

$$Y_2(z) = V_{c2}(t)E_2(z) \quad (4)$$

$$Y(z) = Y_1(z) + Y_2(z) \quad (5)$$

Using these relationships and BPM simulation the performance of the proposed photonic multiplexer is simulated as follows.

Fig. 1. The 1x1 photonic switch (a). Schematic representation and (b). Cross-sectional view.

III. Results and discussion

The coupled-mode theory (CMT)[9] provides the analytical results of the proposed photonic multiplexer without considering the waveguide dimensions and LNoI wafer design parameters. The entire 1x1 photonic switch and photonic multiplexer structure are simulated using the 2D FD-BPM method. When an external driving voltage is applied to the electrode configuration, the electric field distribution between the two electrodes changes the phase of the light propagating through the waveguide, which slows down the light speed and requires different coupling lengths. Hence, the launched light is propagated through the straight waveguide without coupling with the adjacent waveguide. This state we refer to as ON-state of the 1x1 photonic switch. Based on this working principle the two photonic switches in the photonic multiplexer are controlled to maintain in the ON-state as shown in Fig.4(a). In the absence of driving voltage, the light propagation in one waveguide couples with the adjacent waveguide through its evanescent tail. The power in the input waveguide is completely transferred to the adjacent waveguide at a length of coupling length (L_c). Here the adjacent waveguide is connected with the tapered waveguide which acts as the terminated port. This state of operation

is called as OFF-state of the 1x1 photonic switch. Based on this principle, the two photonic switches are maintained in the OFF-state which is the main feature of the proposed photonic multiplexer and the beam propagation result is shown in Fig.4(b).

Fig. 2. The BPM result of 1x1 photonic switch in (a) ON-state and in (b) OFF-state.

Fig. 3. The 2x1 photonic multiplexer.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed and numerically demonstrated a photonic multiplexer using two 1x1 photonic switches based on the directional coupler. The insertion loss of 1.9206 dB is obtained at the optimum operating voltage of 3.3 V. Numerical simulations confirming the photonic multiplexer and various figures of merit are calculated from the simulation results. In conclusion, based on the optimum performance, the photonic multiplexer can be used for the future configurable photonic integrated circuits.

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Fig. 4. The BPM result of 1×1 photonic switch in (a,b) ON-state and in (c) OFF-state.

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